

Alimony in Students of Legal Age as a Fundamental Right to Education

Alex Fabián Solano Moreno¹, Josué Ramón Limaico Mina², Diego Vladimir Garcés Mayorga³,
and Paul Orlando Piray Rodríguez⁴

¹ Universidad Regional Autónoma de Los Andes, Matriz Ambato. Ecuador. E-mail: ua.alexsolano@uniandes.edu.ec

² Universidad Regional Autónoma de Los Andes, Sede Ibarra. Ecuador. E-mail: ui.josuelimaico@uniandes.edu.ec

³ Universidad Regional Autónoma de Los Andes, Sede Puyo. Ecuador. E-mail: up.diegogarcés@uniandes.edu.ec

⁴ Universidad Regional Autónoma de Los Andes, Sede Riobamba. Ecuador. E-mail: ur.paulpr13@uniandes.edu.ec

Abstract. The right to food is closely related to the parent-child relationship and constitutes a right of the children and an obligation of the parents. Ecuadorian regulations seek to guarantee studies even when their children become adults and need to continue their academic training. University students are often forced to abandon their studies due to a lack of economic incentives. The objective of this study is to determine the factors that affect the right to education of students when they reach the age of majority and the negative effects caused by the suspension of alimony. As a result, it is obtained using the neutrosophic TOPSIS method to propose the implementation of legal reforms to extend alimony up to 24 years of age.

Keywords: right to food, education, alimony, neutrosophic TOPSIS.

1 Introduction

The alimony has the function of solving the basic needs of food by the obligor. The right to food is an inalienable, non-transferable, and unattachable right. It is a right that is born and is permanently renewed, as the need for the support of this right changes. This definition includes the essential resources for the subsistence of a person, and the means tending to allow a decent existence [1].

In such virtue, Art. 129 of [2] establishes a logical order of taxes to fulfill this obligation with minors and their exceptions. On the other hand, [3] in Art. 349 regulates this issue in general and introduces the reciprocal nature of the benefit. The Constitution of Ecuador establishes in a guaranteed manner the protection of the rights of children and adolescents within the current Constitutional State of Rights and Social Justice [4].

The State and the family must guarantee the rights of children or adults who are studying up to the age of 21. To protect the right to food, and without leaving them without it because it is a fundamental right, they must acquire a way of life that allows them to have a comprehensive life development, safeguarding the other rights that derive from the aforementioned right [5] [6].

In January, a Legal Reform was proposed to extend the payment of alimony to the age of 24 to support university students. It was cataloged as a big mistake since it is about adults who must learn to earn a living by their own means. The thesis generated controversy and divergent positions. At one extreme are those who claim that this will encourage a generation of irresponsible young people supported by their divorced parents. On the other hand, those who ensure that parents should support their children's university studies, even if they do not live with them [7] [8].

It should be stated that Private Universities receive enormous economic resources from the state even though they are companies destined to make an education business. A faithful example of that is the cost of master's degrees in the country. It is necessary to be objective and observe that they are not minors or adolescents and that they are affected by preventing them from having the power to learn to earn a living by their own means [9] [10].

Economics and education are two fields that maintain a close correlation. Teaching has a fundamental effect on the economic life of people, and, in turn, financial phenomena affect the present and future of education. Among the most prominent problems of school dropout in higher education is that it has been violated by the extinction of alimony to young people who have reached 21 years of age [11].

To analyze the factors that affect the right to education, it is defined as a problem situation: alimony to students over 21 years of age. The main objective of this research is to define the main factors that affect the right to education. Specific objectives: determine the factors that affect the analyzed variable, perform the measurement and modeling of the variable, and finally define the potential alternatives based on eradicating the variables that

affect the fulfillment of the right to education.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Neurosophic statistics

Neurosophic probabilities and statistics are a generalization of classical and imprecise probabilities and statistics. The Neurosophic Probability of event E is the probability that event E will occur, the probability that event E will not occur, and the probability of indeterminacy (not knowing whether event E will occur or not). In classical probability $n_{sup} \leq 1$, while in neurosophic probability $n_{sup} \leq 3+$.

The function that models the neurosophic probability of a random variable x is called the neurosophic distribution:

$$NP(x) = (T(x), I(x), F(x))$$

Where T(x) represents the probability that value x occurs, F(x) represents the probability that value x does not occur, and I(x) represents the undetermined or unknown probability of value x. Neurosophic Statistics is the analysis of neurosophic events and deals with neurosophic numbers, the neurosophic probability distribution [12], neurosophic estimation, neurosophic regression, etc.

It refers to a set of data, which is formed totally or partially by data with some degree of indeterminacy and the methods to analyze them. Neurosophic statistical methods allow neurosophic data (data that may be ambiguous, vague, imprecise, incomplete, or even unknown) to be interpreted and organized to reveal underlying patterns [13].

Finally, the Neurosophic Logic [14], the Neurosophic Sets, and the Neurosophic Probabilities and Statistics have a wide application in various research fields and constitute a new reference for study in full development. Neurosophic Descriptive Statistics comprises all the techniques for summarizing and describing the characteristics of neurosophic numerical data [15].

Neurosophic Numbers are numbers of the form $N = a + bI$ where a and b are real or complex numbers [16], while "I" is the indeterminacy part of the neurosophic number N. The study of neurosophic statistics refers to a neurosophic random variable where X_l and $X_u I_N$ represent the lower and correspondingly higher level that the studied variable can reach, in an indeterminate interval $[I_l, I_u]$. Following the neurosophic mean of the variable ($\bar{x}_N$) by formulating:

$$X_N = X_l + X_u I_N; I_N \in [I_l, I_u] \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Where, } \bar{x}_a = \frac{1}{n_N} \sum_{i=1}^{n_N} X_{il}, \bar{x}_b = \frac{1}{n_N} \sum_{i=1}^{n_N} X_{iu}, n_N \in [n_l, n_u], \tag{2}$$

is a neurosophic random sample. However, for the calculation of neutral squares (NNS), it can be calculated as follows

$$\sum_{i=1}^n N(X_i - \bar{X}_{iN})^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n N \left[\begin{array}{c} \min \left((a_i + b_i I_L)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_L), (a_i + b_i I_L)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_U) \right) \\ (a_i + b_i I_U)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_L), (a_i + b_i I_U)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_U) \\ \max \left((a_i + b_i I_L)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_L), (a_i + b_i I_L)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_U) \right) \\ (a_i + b_i I_U)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_L), (a_i + b_i I_U)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_U) \end{array} \right], I \in [I_L, I_U] \tag{3}$$

Where $a_i = X_l, b_i = X_u$. The variance of the neurosophic sample can be calculated by

$$S_N^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_N} (X_i - \bar{X}_{iN})^2}{n_N}; S_N^2 \in [S_L^2, S_U^2] \tag{4}$$

The neurosophic coefficient (NCV) measures the consistency of the variable. The lower the value of the NCV, the more consistent the performance of the factor is if compared to the other factors. The NCV can be calculated as follows [17].

$$CV_N = \frac{\sqrt{S_N^2}}{\bar{x}_N} \times 100; CV_N \in [CV_L, CV_U] \tag{5}$$

2.2 TOPSIS method

TOPSIS (*Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution*). This technique is characterized by its effectiveness and the simplicity of its principle in solving multi-criteria decision problems. In the case of TOPSIS, the selection is based on finding the alternative that is closest to the ideal solution and, in turn, is further away from the worst solution. It allows combining several heterogeneous attributes in a single dimensionless index, and this is because the attributes under evaluation are very possibly expressed in different units or scales [18].

TOPSIS is based on the concept that the selected alternative must have the smallest Euclidean distance to an ideal solution and the largest Euclidean distance to an anti-ideal solution. So, the order of preference of the alternatives can be determined through a series of comparisons of these distances. Both solutions, the ideal and the anti-ideal, are fictitious.

The ideal solution is a solution for which all attribute values correspond to the optimal values of each attribute contained in the alternatives; the anti-ideal solution is the solution for which all attribute values correspond to the least desired values of each attribute contained in the alternatives. In this way, TOPSIS provides a solution that is not only the closest to a hypothetically better solution but also the farthest from the hypothetically worse one. The process is described below:

1. Determine the objective and identify the attributes to be evaluated.
2. Prepare a matrix based on the information available on the attributes. Each row corresponds to an alternative and each column to an attribute. The element x_j of the array represents the non-normalized value of the j_{th} attribute for the i_{th} alternative.
3. Calculate the normalized decision matrix R_{ij} . This is obtained by dividing each attribute value x_j by the square root of the sum of the squares of each attribute value x_j . This is represented mathematically by equation (6):

$$R_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{m=1}^k x_{mj}^2}} \tag{6}$$

4. Determine the relative importance or weight of each attribute with respect to the objective. This gives rise to a set of weights w_j (for $j = 1, 2, \dots, J$) such that $\sum w_j = 1$. The weights are generally based on expert judgment and should reflect the relative importance assigned to the attributes of evaluated performance. The range of possible values of w_j will only be limited by the ability of the elements of the decision group to distinguish the relative importance of the analyzed performance attributes.
5. Obtain the normalized and weighted matrix V_{ij} . This is done by multiplying each element in the columns of the matrix R_{ij} by its corresponding weight w_j . Therefore, the elements of the normalized and weighted matrix are expressed by equation 7:

6.
$$V_{ij} = w_j * R_{ij} \tag{7}$$

7. Obtain the ideal and anti-ideal solution: The ideal solution can be expressed as (8) and the anti-ideal as (9). V_j^+ indicates the ideal value of the attribute considered among the values of the attributes for the different alternatives, while V_j^- indicates the worst value of the attribute considered among the values of the attributes for the different alternatives [17, 19, 20, 24, 25].

8.
$$V^+ = \{V_1^+, V_2^+, V_3^+, \dots, V_j^+\} \tag{8}$$

$$V^- = \{V_1^-, V_2^-, V_3^-, \dots, V_j^-\} \tag{9}$$

9. Calculate the Euclidean distances of each alternative to the ideal and anti-ideal solutions using the following equations:

$$D_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^j (V_{ij} - V_j^+)^2} \tag{10}$$

$$D_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^j (V_{ij} - V_j^-)^2} \tag{11}$$

10. The relative closeness P_i of a particular alternative to the ideal solution is expressed by (12):

11.
$$P_i = \frac{D_i^-}{(D_i^+ + D_i^-)} \tag{12}$$

12. In this step, a set of alternatives is generated in descending order according to the value of P_i , having as the best alternative the one with the highest value of P_i .

13. In this article, linguistic terms will be associated with SVNN, so that the experts can carry out their evaluations according to the corresponding scale (Table 1).

Linguistic term	SVNN
Very Weak (VW)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)
Weak (W)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)
Medium Weak (MW)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)
Medium (M)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)
Medium Strong (MS)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)
Strong (S)	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)
Very Strong (VS)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)

Table 1. Linguistic terms according to the strength of the weight in the alternatives. Source: own elaboration.

3 Results

After analyzing the different approaches, the techniques described above are applied as follows. For the right to education and due to the complexity and indeterminacy of the data, it was decided to apply neutrosophic statistics for the modeling of the analyzed variable.

From the processing of the information and the consensus of the experts, the factors that most affect the right to education (Table 2) and the variable to be modeled were determined.

Variable analyzed: right to education, for a sample of $n=150$ for each factor (f)

Code	Initials	Factors affecting the right to education
a	RLPF	Reform Legal and Political Frameworks
b	PFCE	Provide Free and Compulsory Education
c	EI	Eliminate Inequalities
d	EF	Education Financing
e	LC	Lack of Compromise

Table 2. Determining factors in the right to education. Source: own elaboration

For the development of the statistical study, the neutrosophic frequencies of the determining factors in the right to education are analyzed, mainly in students of legal age. For each factor, an affectation is analyzed in days that make up the set of affectations to ensure that education is for everyone.

Days	Neutrosophic Frequencies				
	RLPF	PFCE	EI	EF	LC
1	[1 ; 2]	[1 ; 2]	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 1]
2	[1 ; 2]	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 1]	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 1]
3	[1 ; 1]	[0 ; 0]	[1 ; 2]	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 1]
4	[0 ; 0]	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 2]	[0 ; 1]	[1 ; 1]
5	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 1]	[0 ; 1]	[0 ; 1]	[1 ; 2]
6	[1 ; 1]	[0 ; 0]	[1 ; 2]	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 1]
7	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 2]	[0 ; 1]	[0 ; 0]	[1 ; 1]
8	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 1]	[1 ; 2]	[0 ; 0]	[1 ; 1]
9	[1 ; 2]	[0 ; 1]	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 1]	[1 ; 2]
10	[1 ; 2]	[1 ; 1]	[0 ; 1]	[0 ; 0]	[1 ; 1]
11	[1 ; 2]	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 1]	[0 ; 0]
12	[1 ; 2]	[0 ; 1]	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 0]	[1 ; 1]
13	[0 ; 0]	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 1]	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 0]
14	[1 ; 1]	[0 ; 1]	[1 ; 2]	[0 ; 1]	[0 ; 1]
15	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 1]	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 2]

Days	Neutrosophic Frequencies				
	RLPF	PFCE	EI	EF	LC
16	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 2]	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 2]	[1 ; 1]
17	[0 ; 0]	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 2]	[0 ; 1]
18	[1 ; 2]	[0 ; 1]	[0 ; 1]	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 1]
19	[0 ; 0]	[0 ; 1]	[1 ; 2]	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 1]
20	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 1]	[1 ; 1]	[0 ; 1]	[1 ; 2]
0-150	[83 ; 159]	[73 ; 140]	[72 ; 147]	[75 ; 155]	[83 ; 150]

Table 3. Factors that affect the fulfillment of the right to education.

Table 3 studies the factor effects on the fulfillment of the right to education, for 150 days, with an occurrence level of [0; 2] for each factor per day. There is a total indeterminacy level of a=76, b=67, c=75, d=80, e=67, with a representativeness level of [44.66%; 51.61%], on days when 2 affectations per factor were recorded. A 50% higher incidence is observed in *Eliminate Inequalities* and *Provide Free and Compulsory Education*. As a result of the existing indeterminacy, the use of classical statistics is not possible, so the use of neutrosophic statistics is necessary for its greater understanding. [26, 27]

Neutrosophic Statistical Analysis

In the modeling of the data of the affectations that affect education for all young people (Table 4), it will be possible to understand what factor implies a representative mean $\bar{x} = \in [\bar{x}_L; \bar{x}_U]$, the values of the neutrosophic means are calculated, and for the study of the variations of the affectations, the values of the neutrosophic standard deviation $S_N \in [S_L; S_U]$. To determine which affectation requires a greater incidence in the right to education, the values $CV_N \in [CV_L; CV_U]$ are calculated.

Factors	$\bar{x}_N$	S_N	CV_N
<i>Reform Legal and Political Frameworks</i>	[0.553; 1.06]	[0.126; 0.988]	[0.228; 0.932]
<i>Provide Free and Compulsory Education</i>	[0.487; 0.933]	[0.125; 1,015]	[0.257; 1,088]
<i>Eliminate Inequalities</i>	[0.48; 0.98]	[0.125; 0.965]	[0.26; 0.985]
<i>Education Financing</i>	[0.5; 1,033]	[0.125; 1,028]	[0.25; 0.995]
<i>Lack of Compromise</i>	[0.553; 1]	[0.126; 1,018]	[0.228; 1,018]

Table 4. Neutrosophic statistical analysis of the incidences of education. Source: own elaboration

Table 4 shows that reforming legal and political frameworks has higher incidence values than the other factors. This means that the RLPF factor is, on average, the one that has the most impact on compliance with the rights of older students to education. In affirmation of the value of this factor CV_{No} , is lower compared to the others. This means that the result of RLPF has a negative and more significant impact than other factors on the right to education

Comparative analysis

To determine the associated referent uncertainty measure for $\bar{x} = \in [\bar{x}_L; \bar{x}_U]$, $S_N \in [S_L; S_U]$ and $CV_N \in [CV_L; CV_U]$ to the form of neutrosophic numbers (Table 5), it is observed that the CV_N values range from 0.228 to 0.932, with an indeterminacy measure of 75.5. This generates a negative impact on compliance with the reforms to the legal frameworks for better fulfillment of the right to education, as well as its influence on other affectations. The governing bodies are required to focus on a higher level of monitoring of regulations and policies for student training. [21, 22, 23]

Factors	$\bar{x}_N$	S_N	CV_N
<i>RLPF</i>	0.553 + 1.06 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 47.8]	0.126 + 0.988 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 87.2]	0.228 + 0.932 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 75.5]
<i>PFCE</i>	0.487 + 0.933 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 47.8]	0.125 + 1.015 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 87.7]	0.257 + 1.088 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 76.4]
<i>EI</i>	0.48 + 0.98 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 51.0]	0.125 + 0.965 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 87.0]	0.26 + 0.985 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 73.6]

Factors	$\bar{x}_N$	S_N	CV_N
<i>EF</i>	0.5 + 1.033 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 51.6]	0.125 + 1.028 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 87.8]	0.25 + 0.995 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 74.9]
<i>LC</i>	0.553 + 1I; I ∈ [0; 0; 44.7]	0.126 + 1.018 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 87.6]	0.228 + 1.018 I; I ∈ [0; 0; 77.6]

Table 5. Neutrosophic forms with measure of indeterminacy. Source: own elaboration.

TOPSIS analysis

To determine possible alternatives based on using regulations and policies for student training, TOPSIS modeling is used. The strategies to be evaluated are focused on monitoring standards and policies for student training and potentiate the following parameters:

- There is no economic policy in favor of university students over 21 years of age
- Pensions only protect university students up to 21 years of age
- Student desertion from universities
- Change in living standards that facilitated access to universities with the support of parents
- Entry into the labor regime, which limits compliance with permanence in classrooms and university activities
- Cuts on economic aid to the education sector with a negative impact on university students

The results are shown in the following tables:

Alternatives	Submit economic policies	Increase personal income	Maintain pensions until age 24	Equity of resources between universities	Extension of maintenance scholarships to third-level students	Present policies of a social nature
Economic policy	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)
Pensions	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)
Student desertion	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)
Change of standards	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)
Entry into the labor regime	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)
Cuts	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)

Table 6. Weights assigned by the experts to each criterion. Source: own elaboration

Alternatives	Submit economic policies	Increase personal income	Maintain pensions until age 24	Equity of resources between universities	Extension of maintenance scholarships to third-level students	Present policies of a social nature
Economic policy	0.12909	0.03907	0.08025	0.01111	0.01252	0.12867
Pensions	0.19466	0.04639	0.04494	0.01676	0.01888	0.16339
Student desertion	0.19466	0.01367	0.04494	0.01676	0.01888	0.19402
Change of standards	0.12909	0.00781	0.02568	0.01411	0.00318	0.03268
Entry into the labor regime	0.19466	0.03907	0.04494	0.00282	0.00318	0.03268
Cuts	0.19466	0.03077	0.08025	0.00282	0.00318	0.03268

Table 7. Weighted normalized matrix. Source: own elaboration.

Alternative	d-	d+	Ri	Order
Economic policy	0.05099	0.06597	0.43595	5
Pensions	0.11550	0	1	1
Student desertion	0.11198	0.03272	0.77387	4
Change of standards	0.04739	0.07607	0.38385	6
Entry into the labor regime	0.11391	0.00732	0.93957	2
Cuts	0.11265	0.01562	0.87818	3

Table 8. Matrix of the distances and calculation of the Ri for each alternative. Source: own elaboration.

From the results obtained, it is preferred to promote alternative 1, relative to alimony or alternative 2, entry into the labor regime, depending on the deficiency to be eradicated. Third-level students, once they reach the age of majority, are often forced to drop out and others look for work and end up leaving the university because their economic solvency does not allow them to continue their university studies.

- Propose a legal reform to the governing bodies and the State with the proposal to extend up to 24 years the payment of alimony to support college students
- Propose aid programs for university students over 21 years of age, who are backed by a difficult economic situation.

Conclusion

The right to education is often violated due to the effectiveness of the application of current legal regulations. In Ecuador, there is a need to design a reform proposal, which introduces the suspension of alimony after 24 years. The Government must encourage and indicate to the governing bodies in the legal field the revision of the current legislation. It is necessary to protect students of legal age, whose parents suspend their alimony when they turn 21 regardless of whether they pursue a university course.

Propose reforms on alimony and aid programs for university students over 21 years of age, who are facing a difficult economic situation and are still pursuing higher education.

The method applied seeks to promote alternatives to improve the educational situation in Ecuador. The need to extend alimony up to 24 years of age is formulated so that all young people have the right not only to education and a university degree but also to a job and a decent life.

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